

THE ANNE ARUNDEL COMMUNITY COLLEGE

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Dear reader,

We are delighted to present the fifth annual volume of the *Anne Arundel Community College Journal of Emerging Scholarship* — a milestone that reflects five years of growing student curiosity, rigorous inquiry, and scholarly achievement at AACC.

In 2026, as technological advances, environmental challenges, and societal shifts continue to reshape our world at an unprecedented pace, the value of undergraduate research has never been clearer. Our student authors have tackled timely and timeless questions — exploring innovations in science and technology, examining pressing social and environmental issues, and contributing fresh perspectives across the humanities and beyond. Their work demonstrates that meaningful scholarship begins not in distant laboratories or elite institutions, but right here in our classrooms, libraries, and community.

What makes this journal possible is the remarkable collaboration between talented students and dedicated faculty mentors. Every manuscript has undergone a thoughtful review process, helping students develop essential skills in critical thinking, persistence, and professional communication that will serve them well whether they transfer to four-year institutions or enter the workforce.

We hope that readers — fellow students, faculty, staff, community members, and external scholars — will find inspiration in these pages. May the research presented here spark new questions, encourage future submissions, and affirm that every voice has the potential to contribute to the ever-growing body of knowledge.

Sincerely,

The 2025–2026 Editorial Board

2025–2026 EDITORIAL BOARD

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From Shelf to Self: Assessing the Journey of *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG Survival in Various Beverages

KEY WORDS

Lactobacillus rhamnosus GG

GI tract

probiotics

in vitro model

Monster Energy®

coffee

FACULTY MENTOR

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ABSTRACT

Because of their potential health benefits, the probiotic supplement market has grown exponentially into a global multi-billion-dollar industry. Consumers use probiotics to support gastrointestinal (GI) and immune health. However, their efficacy depends on their ability to survive the harsh conditions of the GI tract, colonize the intestines, and outcompete other microbes. Understanding probiotic survivability in the GI tract, while accounting for real-world scenarios, is vital for both producers and consumers. In a previous study, it was determined that the commonly used probiotic strain, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG (LGG), in tablet form, survived passage through an *in vitro* simulated upper GI tract model. Probiotics are available in various forms, including capsules that are commonly administered with water. This study examined the survival of encapsulated LGG when administered with three commonly consumed beverages in a simulated upper intestinal tract model. Results revealed an increase in LGG survivability in the gastric environment with acidic beverages (coffee [average 2.49×10^7 CFU/mL], Monster Energy® [average 2.14×10^7 CFU/mL]) as

compared to water (average 9.67×10^6 CFU/mL). In contrast, LGG survivability was similar between three beverages in the duodenal stage, as determined by CFU/mL counts and microscopy. This paper will compare the findings with those of the previous study and address the effects of beverages on drug activity and absorption.

INTRODUCTION

Background

Probiotics are viable microorganisms that have measurable health benefits when consumed in specific amounts (Bayer et al., 2025). Probiotic strains can be found in dietary supplements and naturally fermented foods (cheese, yogurt, sauerkraut, kimchi, kefir) (Bayer et al., 2025). Probiotic research focuses on seven primary microbial genera: *Bacillus*, *Bifidobacterium*, *Enterococcus*, *Escherichia*, *Lactobacillus*, *Saccharomyces*, and *Streptococcus* (Bayer et al., 2025).

Lactobacillus: Many probiotics contain bacteria from the Lactobacillaceae family, including several species formerly in the genus *Lactobacillus* (National Institutes of Health, 2025). The *Lactobacillus* genus consists of Gram-positive bacteria commonly found in the human mouth, gastrointestinal (GI) tract, and genitourinary tract as part of the normal microbiota (McBroom, 2022). These bacteria account for 6% of the total GI tract bacterial population (Du et al., 2022), and only 0.01 to 0.06% (10^5 to 10^8 CFU/g) of all adult fecal bacterial species (Zhang et al., 2018). *Lactobacillus* species inhibit pathogens by producing lactic acid, thereby benefiting human health (Bayer et al., 2025). The most used *Lactobacillus* strain in probiotic research, supplements, and clinical studies is *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG (LGG) (Bayer et al., 2025). In 1900, Ernst Moro isolated LGG from healthy human feces and found that it colonized the gut significantly more than other *Lactobacillus* species (Bayer et al., 2025). The ability of LGG to outcompete pathogenic microbes and specifically adhere to the

intestinal mucosa and epithelium (Bayer et al., 2025) makes this strain a strong probiotic candidate.

Implications

The human GI tract harbors a diverse microbial ecosystem that profoundly influences immune activity and metabolism. In a medically referenced man weighing 70 kg, there are approximately the same number of human cells in the body (3.0×10^{13}) as there are gut microbiota in the colon (3.8×10^{13}) (Sender et al., 2016). Therefore, consuming a probiotic to support the healthy function of the gut microbiota is desirable.

GI tract symptom relief and a desire to promote overall health have been cited as determinants of probiotic consumption (Bayer et al., 2025). Dosage and strain variation of probiotics influence their effectiveness for enzymatic activity targeting, gut barrier reinforcement, immunomodulation, and pathogen competition (Bayer et al., 2025). Studies show that mood and cognition in older adults, acute gastroenteritis, and irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) can improve with probiotic consumption (Bayer et al., 2025). While the aforementioned studies report a wide range of health benefits, Grazul et al. (2016) found that probiotic colonization is not required for a positive influence on the gut microbiota (as cited in Bayer et al., 2025).

Because of their potential health benefits, the probiotic industry has seen substantial growth. In 2025, the probiotics industry was estimated to be worth approximately \$114.31 billion USD (Pandey & Shivarkar, 2025), up from \$73.65 billion in 2023 (Bayer et al., 2025), representing a \$40.66 billion growth in 2 years. Conversely, the forecast for 2035 is \$429.01 billion (Pandey & Shivarkar, 2025). Asia Pacific accounts for 39% of the global market share of probiotic use, while the US accounts for 28% (Pandey & Shivarkar, 2025). Parker et al. (2018) determined that 3.9 million people in the US consumed probiotics in 2015, which

was 4 times higher than in 2007 (as cited in Bayer et al., 2025).

To be effective, probiotic microbes that are released from the supplement must survive the GI gauntlet by traveling from the mouth, through the stomach, and eventually into the intestine to colonize (Bayer et al., 2025). Probiotic release is defined as the total number of organisms that escape the supplement as compared to probiotic survivability, which refers to the number of viable cells remaining after release. Bayer et al. (2025) determined that LGG within a Culturelle® chewable tablet remained viable after reaching the intestines following digestion. Probiotics, such as Culturelle®, are available in various forms, including chewable tablets and capsules. Therefore, these supplements must be consumed differently to deliver the probiotic strains to the duodenum. The probiotic strains in the Culturelle® tablets are encased in microcrystalline cellulose (MCC), whereas those in capsules are encased in a soluble film made from hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC). The encapsulated probiotic strains require liquids to initiate dissolution and to activate LGG, as these supplements are swallowed whole. Patient body position and water volume (average 118.7 mL for capsules; minimum 60 mL) used affected medication effectiveness, as capsules and tablets can adhere to the esophagus and can be difficult to dislodge (Fuchs, 2009).

Beverage Effects on Drugs: Water is the preferred liquid for taking most medications, as other beverages and foods can affect drug absorption and action (Safemedicationuse.ca, 2012; Swearingen, 2024). For example, more than 85 medications have been documented to interact with grapefruit juice (Chen et al., 2018). Grapefruit juice is reported to increase drug absorption, such as statins, leading to tissue damage or overdose (Chen et al., 2018; Food and Drug Administration, 2021). The natural organic compounds found in grapefruit juice, furanocoumarins, block intestinal enzymes, like cytochrome P450 3A4 (CYP3A4), which assist in the metabolism of many drugs (Hung et al., 2017; De Castro et al.,

2006; Chen et al., 2018; Food and Drug Administration, 2021). Grapefruit juice has been shown to block transporters that facilitate drug absorption, thereby reducing effectiveness (Chen et al., 2018).

Beverage pH has been shown to affect drug activity and absorbance. One study found that the absorbance of the anti-fungal drug ketoconazole improved when taken with Coca-Cola Classic (pH 2.5, 240 mL) as compared with water (240 mL) in patients with drug-induced achlorhydria, a condition where proton pump inhibitors (PPI's) are taken long-term suppressing stomach acid to the point where little to no hydrochloric acid (HCl) is produced (Chin et al., 1995). Drug release from certain formulations (pH-dependent sustained-release matrix tablets [such as alginate-based matrix tablets]) and from drugs containing pH-dependent excipients (such as calcium sulfate dehydrate) has been shown to be affected by changes in gastric pH (Abuhelwa et al., 2017). Disintegration or premature release of enteric-coated tablets in the stomach can occur when gastric pH is elevated (less acidic), which diminishes their bioavailability (Wang et al., 2025b).

The temperature of the beverage may affect drug absorption and effectiveness. For example, both cold (4°C) and hot (50°C) drinks can inhibit gastric emptying (Sun et al., 1988). Higher temperatures, such as those above 25°C, can degrade many medications and excipients (Batchelor, 2015).

Beverages with high levels of caffeine can interfere with drug activity. High coffee intake (over 300 mg of caffeine per day) has been shown to affect drug activity, including medications for cold and allergy, depression, high blood pressure, asthma, osteoporosis, anemia, Alzheimer's disease, thyroid conditions, and insomnia (Salamon, 2024). For some medications, caffeine can reduce or eliminate their therapeutic effect, increase side effects, or even block absorption completely (Quill, 2025).

Besides drug activity and absorbance, beverage content can influence the chemical and nutritional hospitability of the

gastrointestinal environment (Leiper, 2015). Food content (e.g., polyunsaturated fatty acids, carbohydrates, proteins) and plant extracts can promote or inhibit the effectiveness of probiotics (Ranadheera et al., 2010). This concept should apply to beverages as well. A 2025 study showed that LGG survivability increased when consuming probiotics with (5.39–5.92 log CFU/g) or after a meal (5.19–6.38 log CFU/g) as compared to taking a probiotic on an empty stomach (4.93–6.04 log CFU/g) (Wang et al., 2025a). Although a different medium, this would suggest that beverage content might also moderate LGG survivability compared to an empty stomach.

Beverage Types: From 2015 to 2018, water accounted for 51.2% of total nonalcoholic beverage consumption daily among adults, aged 20 and over, in the United States, followed by coffee (14.9%), sweetened beverages (including energy drinks) (10.2%), tea (8.7%), fruit beverages (5.6%), milk (5.5%), and diet beverages (3.8%) (Martin et al., 2020). Although water is the most consumed beverage, coffee and energy drink consumption is on the rise.

Coffee is the most common beverage consumed at breakfast by adults in the U.S., according to a Food Surveys Research Group report (Sebastian et al., 2024). Per the International Coffee Organization (ICO) Coffee Market Report (2025), the world's coffee consumption is estimated at 180.2 million 60 kg bags per year, which, according to the USDA Foreign Agricultural Service (2025), outpaces the world's estimated production of 178.7 million 60 kg bags (as cited in Arms, 2025). Further, Statistica's Coffee Market Forecast (2025) estimated the total annual industry revenue at \$485.59 billion USD, with \$380.22 billion spent outside the home and \$105.37 billion spent on at-home use (as cited in Arms, 2025). Given the ubiquity of coffee consumption, it is highly probable that consumers co-administer probiotics with their morning coffee.

Similar to coffee, energy drink consumption is on the rise.

The Statista Consumer Market Outlook estimates energy drink sales to be approximately \$208 billion USD as of 2024, with a forecast of more than \$248 billion in 2029 (as cited in Ridder, 2025). As of 2024, the U.S. is the market leader in per capita sales, at \$21 billion USD (Ridder, 2025). While many sources identify Red Bull® as the leading energy drink, statistics from a-insights indicate that in 2021, Monster Energy® sold more units (14.7 billion units, \$5.54 billion USD) than Red Bull® (9.8 billion units, \$8.24 billion USD), making it the most popular beverage (as cited in van der Pijl, 2022).

As probiotic microbes must be alive in specific amounts to have a positive influence on health, the type of beverage used to consume the capsule may affect how much culture reaches the duodenum of the small intestine. Since water is not always used for probiotic capsule delivery, this study focused on the impact of commonly consumed beverages, such as coffee and Monster Energy®, on the survival of encapsulated LGG in a simulated GI environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Organism Used in the Study

Before each trial, each capsule was weighed and recorded. According to the manufacturer, the colony-forming units (CFUs) were counted at the point of expiration and reported as 10 billion CFUs of LGG ATCC 53103 (Culturelle®, n.d.; Well.ca, n.d.).

Beverages Used in the Study

The beverages in this study included the following: Colombian medium-roast blend coffee (7-Eleven™), Monster Energy® Zero Sugar Ultra Paradise energy drink, and pre-bottled water (Deer Park® Spring Water, control). To determine a standard beverage volume, each researcher sipped water and collected it into a clean graduated cylinder to simulate oral medication consumption. The

average water volume consumed was recorded as 42 mL. Note: this model does not account for additional beverage volumes individuals may consume beyond the calculated standard sip.

Simulated Upper Intestinal Tract Model

The protocol used in this study is based on the *in vitro* model described by Bayer et al. (2025) with minor adjustments (Figure 1).

LGG survivability was measured during the stomach and up-

per small intestine (duodenum) stages of the GI tract (Bayer et al., 2025). Digestive enzymes, mechanical forces, pH, and temperature were adjusted as needed. A total of 7 trials were run. However, trials 1–4 were excluded due to procedural inconsistencies.

Experiment Set-Up: All samples were treated as follows: Beverages were stored at room temperature, unopened. Prior to each trial, pre-measured beverage samples (42 mL, using a sterile graduated cylinder) were poured into 50 mL conical tubes. Simulated gastric fluid (SGF) was prepared with sterile H₂O and 0.1 M HCl (pH 2.0, total volume of 35 mL). The beverages and SGF were incubated at 37°C to mimic body temperature.

Stomach Stage: The pre-measured beverage, the pre-weighed probiotic capsule, and SGF were combined in a 250 mL sterile glass Erlenmeyer flask with a rubber stopper. The beverage pH was recorded before and after the addition of the SGF and probiotic capsule. Then, a Porcine Pepsin solution (2.3 mL, Sigma-Aldrich, 2 mg/mL in 10 mM HCl, filter-sterilized) was added and mixed

FIGURE 1

Schematic of the Simulated

Upper Intestinal Tract Model

by swirling into the beverage-SGF-capsule solution. The mixed stomach solution was incubated at 37°C with shaking at 135 rpm for 8 minutes to simulate gastric peristalsis. This time was selected as water in an empty stomach can take 5 to 20 minutes to leave the stomach (Watson, 2025). After incubation, 1.0 M NaOH was added to each stomach solution (final pH of 6.0) and briefly swirled to neutralize the GI environment and deactivate pepsin. After stomach solution neutralization, samples were collected for microscopy and bacterial enumeration by serial dilutions.

Upper Small Intestinal Stage: To recreate conditions in the small intestines, specifically the duodenum, Bovine Alpha-Chymotrypsin and Trypsin (2.3 mL each, 5 mg/mL, filter-sterilized, pH 6.5 in 10 mM Na₃PO₄, Sigma-Aldrich) were added to the neutralized stomach solutions and swirled. The enzyme-treated solutions were incubated at 37°C with shaking at 65 rpm for 20 minutes to simulate intestinal peristalsis. After incubation, samples were collected for microscopy and serial dilution.

Bacterial Enumeration

To determine the number of viable bacteria (LGG survivability), CFU per mL of culture was obtained as follows: After each stage, a 100 µL sample was collected and serially diluted 10-fold (10⁰ to 10⁹) in sterile De Man-Rogosa-Sharpe (MRS) Broth (HIMEDIA). At this point, 100 µL of each dilution was spread-plated onto sterile MRS Agar plates (DIFCO). The agar plates were incubated in a sealed jar with a lit tealight candle at 37°C for 48–72 hours to simulate anaerobic conditions. Prior to incubation, a weigh boat containing baking soda was placed inside the jar to reduce condensation. After incubation, agar plates containing 30 to 300 colonies were used for the final CFU count, with multiple countable plates averaged. To calculate the CFU per mL of culture, the following formula was used: (Number of Colonies [CFUs] X Dilution Factor)/mL plated.

Microscopy

After each stage, a 100 μL sample (200 μL total) was stained using the simple and Gram stains for viewing at 10X, 40X, and 100X. Simple staining with Methylene Blue was performed to determine the size, morphology, and arrangement of the probiotic bacteria

TABLE 1 Colony Counts of the Probiotic Strain After Each Stage of the Simulated Upper Intestinal Tract Model for Three Beverage Treatments

Trial	Beverage	Plate ID	Colony Count	CFU/mL
Trial #5	Water	Stomach #5	50	5.00E+06
		Duodenum #5	287*	2.87E+07
	Coffee	Stomach #5	197	1.97E+07
		Duodenum #5	45	4.50E+07
	Monster Energy®	Stomach #5	260*	2.60E+07
		Duodenum #5	37	3.70E+07
Trial #6	Water	Stomach #6	140	1.40E+07
		Duodenum #6	347*	3.47E+07
	Coffee	Stomach #6	337*	3.37E+07
		Duodenum #6	368*	3.68E+07
	Monster Energy®	Stomach #6	120	1.20E+07
		Duodenum #6	90	9.00E+06
Trial #7	Water	Stomach #7	100	1.00E+07
		Duodenum #7	44	4.40E+07
	Coffee	Stomach #7	212	2.12E+07
		Duodenum #7	36	3.60E+07
	Monster Energy®	Stomach #7	261*	2.61E+07
		Duodenum #7	65	6.50E+07

An asterisk (*) indicates multiple countable plates, and the CFU represents an average.

and to detect viability through Brownian motion. Gram staining was performed to verify the presence of Gram-positive bacilli, which is indicative of lactobacilli. In addition, staining was used to evaluate the degradation of the HPMC capsule at each stage.

RESULTS

Bacterial Cell Counts

To determine LGG survivability in a capsule under simulated conditions in the upper digestive tract, colony counts and microscopy were performed after each stage. The initial pH of water, coffee, and Monster Energy® drink were approximately 6.5, 5, and 4, respectively. The initial weights of the capsules ranged from 37.6 mg to 39.8 mg. After adding the SGF solution, the final gastric pH ranged from 3.5 (water) to 4 (coffee, Monster Energy®). Colony counts were recorded after each stage using the various beverages (Table 1).

After the stomach stage, the average CFUs per mL of culture were 2.49×10^7 (coffee), 2.14×10^7 (Monster Energy®), and 9.67×10^6 (water) (Table 2, Figure 2). After the upper small intestine (duodenum) stage, the average CFUs per mL of culture were 3.93×10^7 (coffee), 3.70×10^7 (Monster Energy®), and 3.58×10^7 (water) (Table 2, Figure 3).

TABLE 2 Mean CFU/mL of the Probiotic Strain After Each Stage of the Simulated Upper Intestinal Tract Model for Three Beverage Treatments

Beverage	Stage	Trial 5 (CFU/mL)	Trial 6 (CFU/mL)	Trial 7 (CFU/mL)	Mean
Water	Stomach	5.00E+06	1.40E+07	1.00E+07	9.67E+06
	Duodenum	2.87E+07	3.47E+07	4.40E+07	3.58E+07
Coffee	Stomach	1.97E+07	3.37E+07	2.12E+07	2.49E+07
	Duodenum	4.50E+07	3.68E+07	3.60E+07	3.93E+07
Monster Energy®	Stomach	2.60E+07	1.20E+07	2.61E+07	2.14E+07
	Duodenum	3.70E+07	9.00E+06	6.50E+07	3.70E+07

FIGURE 2 *LGG Viability (CFU/mL) Across Different Beverages Under Simulated Gastric Conditions.* A Culturelle® Probiotic Capsule immersed in various beverages (Water, Coffee, Monster Energy®) was exposed to a simulated upper intestinal tract model. A 100 μ L sample was collected and serially diluted 10-fold (10^0 to 10^9) in sterile De Man-Rogosa-Sharpe (MRS) Broth. A total of 100 μ L of each dilution was spread-plated onto sterile MRS Agar plates and incubated anaerobically at 37°C for 48–72 hours. The CFU per mL of culture was calculated using the following formula: (Number of Colonies [CFUs] X Dilution Factor)/mL plated.

FIGURE 3 *LGG Viability (CFU/mL) Across Different Beverages Under Simulated Upper Intestinal Conditions.* A Culturelle® Probiotic Capsule immersed in various beverages (Water, Coffee, Monster Energy®) was exposed to a simulated upper intestinal tract model. A 100 μ L sample was collected and serially diluted 10-fold (10^0 to 10^9) in sterile De Man-Rogosa-Sharpe (MRS) Broth. A total of 100 μ L from each dilution was spread-plated onto sterile MRS Agar plates and incubated anaerobically at 37°C for 48–72 hours. The CFU per mL of culture was calculated using the following formula: (Number of Colonies [CFUs] X Dilution Factor)/mL plated.

Microscopy

To monitor the progress of the probiotic capsule, simple (Figure 4) and Gram (Figure 5) stains were completed after each stage. Staining revealed the presence of single bacilli ($3\ \mu\text{m}$ long x $1\ \mu\text{m}$ wide) at all stages, either with blue (Figure 4) or pink (Figure 5) gelatinous material. Brownian motion was apparent in all the simple stain preparations (Figure 4). There were more visible bacteria and gelatinous masses present in the coffee (Figures 4C, 4D, 5C,

FIGURE 4

Simple Stains of the Probiotic Capsule After Each Stage of the Simulated Upper Intestinal Tract Model. A Culturrelle® Probiotic Capsule immersed in various beverages (Water [Figure 4A, 4B], Coffee [Figure 4C, 4D], Monster Energy® [Figure 4E, 4F]) was exposed to a simulated upper intestinal tract model. A 100 μL sample was collected and stained with Methylene Blue at the end of the stomach (Figure 4A, C, E) and duodenum stages (Figure 4B, D, F). A gray arrow indicates a single bacillus, and black arrows indicate gelatinous masses. Samples were viewed at 100X magnification.

and 5D) and Monster Energy® (Figures 4E, 4F, 5E, and 5F) samples than in the water control (Figures 4A, 4B, 5A, and 5B). Single purple bacilli were present in the Gram stain samples (Figure 5).

FIGURE 5

Gram Stains of the Probiotic Capsule After Each Stage of the Simulated Upper Intestinal Tract Model. A Culturrelle® Probiotic Capsule immersed in various beverages (Water [Figure 5A, 5B], Coffee [Figure 5C, 5D], Monster Energy® [Figure 5E, 5F]) was exposed to a simulated upper intestinal tract model. A 100 μ L sample was collected and stained with the Gram Stain at the end of the stomach (Figure 5A, C, E) and duodenum stages (Figure 5B, D, F). Black arrows indicate single bacilli. Samples were viewed at 100x magnification.

DISCUSSION

Similarities to Bayer et al.: This study examined the survivability of encapsulated probiotic strains across different beverage delivery methods in a simulated upper intestinal tract model. There are

several similarities between this study and the work by Bayer et al. (2025). Both studies used Culturelle® products, which contain only one bacterium, LGG, a strain clinically shown to survive the GI tract (Capurso, 2019), thereby eliminating any anomalies associated with multiple-strain interactions. Other considerations for selecting this probiotic include the same starting CFU count (10 billion CFUs) (Culturelle®, n.d.), its ability to survive difficult physiological conditions, its adherence strength (Bayer et al., 2025), its availability, and its established market popularity. The simulated upper intestinal tract model used in both studies had similar pH and enzyme levels, and the data were collected in the same manner (CFU counts, microscopy).

Differences from the Bayer et al. work: While similar, the studies differ in many aspects.

Probiotic Product: Different probiotic forms were used: a chewable tablet vs. a capsule, to examine a different aspect of probiotic survival. Although the starting bacterial count is the same, the product amount differs (tablet: 53 mg, capsule: 40 mg) (Culturelle®, n.d.). This may be due to differences in tablet manufacturing (drying, mixing, and compression), which diminish the bioavailability of the probiotic active components as compared with capsules (Wang et al., 2022). Therefore, to have the same starting CFU numbers, more probiotic strains may need to be added to the tablet. The composition of the probiotic product is different depending on its form. Powdered strains were mixed and compressed with MCC and several other ingredients (xylitol, magnesium stearate, stearic acid, malic acid, citric acid, and natural flavors) to form a tablet, while encapsulated probiotics are produced by putting the powdered strain into a capsule made of HPMC with three other ingredients (200 mg inulin as a prebiotic, magnesium stearate, and titanium dioxide) (Culturelle®, n.d.). The tablet form of the probiotic is not the preferred dosage form (Wang et al., 2022). However, tablets hold a high share of

the global market because they are physiochemically stable, offer manufacturing benefits (simpler processes, lower costs), and are accepted by customers (Wang et al., 2022). The processing of probiotic strains into these different forms could impact the number of starting CFUs used in the experiments. Some of the differences in product content are due to the tablet's orange flavoring (citric acid and other acids), which could affect the product's starting pH.

Delivery Method: The Bayer et al. (2025) trials were conducted with sodium phosphate buffer only (pH 6.5), whereas these trials were conducted with coffee (pH 5.0), Monster Energy® (pH 4.0), and water (pH 6.0) with varying starting pH levels with the purpose of trying to assess the effect of probiotic delivery medium on probiotic survivability in the simulated upper intestinal tract model. The capsules are designed to withstand the highly acidic gastric environment and release their contents in the near-neutral duodenal environment. Acidic (coffee and Monster Energy®) and neutral beverages (Deer Park® Spring Water) were tested and demonstrated higher survival rates in the encapsulated form than in the tablet form. Higher acidic beverages may preemptively accelerate the breakdown of capsule shells, thereby reducing probiotic survivability.

This study used a different delivery system that would influence the simulated upper intestinal tract model. The tablet strains were delivered by chewing the tablet (Bayer et al., 2025), thereby exposing them to the enzymes and pH of the mouth and saliva. However, capsules, by design, largely bypass the mouth environment and enter the stomach almost immediately after oral administration with a liquid, typically limiting exposure to the mouth to six seconds (Chisaka et al., 2007). *In vitro* studies on multiple *Lactobacillus* strains reported no significant decreases in bacterial numbers upon exposure to saliva as compared with the control group (Haukioja et al., 2006; García-Ruiz et al., 2014); thus, the impact of saliva on probiotic strain survivability appears

to be minimal (Han et al., 2021). As a result, the mouth stage was bypassed, and this study started with the stomach stage, with the capsule added to the beverages and SGF. In the previous experiment, 0.2 mL of pepsin was used in the SGF, whereas this study used 2.3 mL to accommodate the increased starting volume (42 mL).

Glucose Supplementation: In the Bayer et al. (2025) study, glucose was added to support LGG growth, whereas this study did not require it. This difference may be due to the use of a different culture medium brand (DIFCO vs. HIMEDIA) with potentially different starting pH levels and subtle differences in nutrient concentrations that could influence bacterial growth on agar plates.

Result Comparison: Based on viable cell count and microscopy, results show that LGG can survive the simulated upper intestinal tract model through all trials, similar to what was observed in the Bayer et al. study. Brownian motion was noted on microscopy, confirming viability. However, in both the stomach and duodenum stages, Monster Energy® and Coffee had, on average, more CFUs than water. However, differences were observed across stages. This could be due to the relationship between the beverage acidity and the HPMC capsule. Specifically, a reduction in LGG survivability or viable cells observed in the water/SGF may be attributed to the lower pH (3.5) as compared to coffee/SGF (pH 4) and Monster Energy® /SGF (pH 4), as pH affects capsule integrity, and thus, early LGG release. If there was an early release of LGG from the encapsulated probiotic in the stomach due to premature capsule degradation, this could lead to a decrease in LGG survivability and decreased probiotic effectiveness. Another explanation is that there is less LGG survivability due to less LGG being released from the capsule when water is used as compared to the other beverages. Based on the microscopic observations, there are less bacteria in the water samples as compared to the other beverages (Figures 3 and 4).

Stomach Stage: An increase in bacterial survivability was observed in the gastric stage with coffee (2.49×10^7 CFU/mL) and Monster Energy® drinks (2.14×10^7 CFU/mL) as compared to water (9.67×10^6 CFU/mL) (Tables 1 and 2, Figures 2, 4, and 5). After the probiotic reaches the stomach, it is exposed to the acidic gastric environment where most acid-sensitive probiotic strains are killed (Han et al., 2021). Ones that survive have a reduction in F1F0-ATPase proton pump activity, which increases probiotic strain survival under low pH conditions (Han et al., 2021; Yao et al., 2020). However, probiotics must endure these acidic conditions for five minutes to two hours, posing a challenge to their survival (Yao et al., 2020). Besides acidity, probiotic viability is affected by other gastric components, including stomach enzymes (pepsin), ionic strength, and mechanical churning (Sarao and Arora, 2017; Surono et al., 2018). Thus, damaged capsules that release probiotic strains prematurely in the stomach may decrease strain survival and thereby decrease effectiveness.

Duodenum Stage: Approximately the same number of bacteria survived the duodenum stage for each beverage (water: 3.58×10^7 , coffee: 3.93×10^7 , Monster: 3.70×10^7), demonstrating that survival levels were consistent and did not differ between beverages (Tables 1 and 2, Figures 2–5). The numbers from the duodenum stage were higher than what was observed for the gastric stage (Tables 1 and 2, Figures 3–5). Therefore, any pre-mature LGG release in the stomach could be irrelevant, as a larger number of LGG are surviving in the duodenum, regardless of the beverage, which is the intended site for LGG.

Comparison to Bayer et al.: Bayer et al. (2025) found that the LGG CFU/mL counts in a simulated upper intestinal tract model (mouth: 5.90×10^8 , stomach: 5.12×10^3 , intestine/duodenum: 1.16×10^3 , Control: 1.17×10^9), were lower than this study (stomach [water: 9.67×10^6 , coffee: 2.49×10^7 , Monster Energy®: 2.14×10^7], intestine/duodenum [water: 3.58×10^7 , coffee: $3.93 \times$

10^7 , Monster Energy[®]: 3.70×10^7) (Tables 1 and 2, Figures 2–5). Neither study had all 10 billion CFUs survive as was expected, since many of the probiotic strains died in the simulated gastric tract. Even the Bayer et al. control, a tablet in sodium phosphate buffer (1.17×10^9), did not yield the manufacturer-reported CFUs.

As mentioned, in the Bayer et al. study, fewer bacteria survived as the probiotic progressed through the GI tract than in this study. This could be that there are fewer bacteria 1) at the start (different processing), 2) that survived the simulated upper intestinal tract model (additional exposure to the mouth conditions, including lysozyme and longer exposure to the stomach [1 hour vs. 8 minutes] and duodenum [1 hour vs. 20 minutes] conditions), or 3) were freed from the MCC material. This could be confirmed by adding a mouth stage and longer incubation times to the experimental setup.

LIMITATIONS

As indicated by Bayer et al. (2025), simulated upper intestinal tract models do not capture the complexities of the GI tract, as microbial survival is influenced by competing bacteria, bile salts, and mucous membranes. Sumeri et al. (2008) observed that LGG experienced up to 6 log-decreases when bile salts were added (as cited in Millette et al., 2013). Other digestive enzymes were excluded because LGG demonstrates proton-prevention and intestinal-barrier protection, allowing it to resist acid (Mathipa-Mdakane & Thantsha, 2022).

Long-term probiotic effectiveness is influenced by colonization resistance provided by the gut microbiota. Some studies (Kristensen et al., 2016; Bazanella et al., 2017; Laursen et al., 2017) have shown that probiotics cannot alter existing gut microbiota (as cited in Han et al., 2021). Variations in host-specific factors, such as underlying health conditions, gut microbiota residency, immunocompromised status, and metabolic activity, limit

the generalizability of *in vitro* findings (Bayer et al., 2025). Those with underlying health conditions experience intestinal dysbiosis, which affects microbial abundance and their function (Afzaal et al., 2022). Methodological limitations, including bacterial distribution, colony density, and delivery systems, may lead to variability in CFU counts. Formulation-specific factors should be considered when comparing results between capsule and chewable delivery formats. Han et al. (2021) found that microencapsulation of probiotics increases survivability (as cited in Bayer et al., 2025).

IMPLICATIONS

The findings from this study further support LGG survivability under the adverse conditions, such as acidity and peristalsis, and its potential as a probiotic for human health.

Formulation-dependent delivery, as well as beverages consumed, has valuable implications for probiotic therapeutic strategies based on the observations in this study. Differences in delivery formats (capsules vs chewable tablets) and beverage consumption (coffee, Monster Energy®, or water) may affect probiotic stability and survival in the GI tract. Understanding the differences in these delivery methods is critical in supporting diverse consumer practices and dietary preferences. Academically, this study extends the work of Bayer et al. (2025) and advances research on the survival of probiotics in a simulated *in vitro* stomach and duodenum model.

FUTURE RESEARCH

As mentioned in Bayer et al. (2025), this probiotic study provides additional insight into the survivability of LGG in a simulated upper intestinal tract model by examining LGG survival when administered via various beverages. A study of LGG survivability in foods using this model would provide an additional angle. Variations of delivery methods may support both consumers and producers in

making informed decisions (Bayer et al., 2025). Probiotic efficacy results should be reviewed under specific conditions, such as variations in medication use and differences in underlying health conditions. Fevers can have severe effects on major organ systems, specifically the liver and GI systems, altering medication efficacy due to protein denaturation when the core body temperature exceeds 104°F (Balli et al., 2025). Medications that alter gastric pH potentially affect probiotic survivability. It is estimated that about 1/4 of all adults globally are prescribed PPIs at some point in their lives, and 1/4 of that group took PPIs for longer than a year (Shanika et al, 2023). The actual percentage of adults who take PPIs in the United States may be higher, as the FDA approved Omeprazole (Prilosec). This medication reduces stomach acid and is available over-the-counter in 2015 to treat conditions like heartburn, acid reflux, and GERD (Cleveland Clinic 2026). Numerous studies have shown that PPIs alter the intestinal microbiome, which is associated with functional dyspepsia, small bowel intestinal overgrowth, and *C. difficile*-associated disease, underscoring the relevance of both probiotics and PPIs (Tian et al., 2023). These insights provide a foundation for subsequent studies.

Additionally, methodological improvements, such as timing of digestion, pH conditions, temperature changes, and enzymatic activity, could better reflect conditions in the GI tract. Refining the SGF mixture to simulate the natural environment by adding sodium chloride and lecithin (Marques et al., 2011) supports a more realistic GI model. A bionic gastrointestinal reactor (BGR) constructed from flexible silicon can more accurately simulate the internal surface texture and flexible structure of the GI tract (Li et al., 2020). For evaluating and recording pH changes, a digital pH photometer would provide objective readings. Further evaluation of different sugars and a wider range of beverages used in probiotic consumption would provide more data to establish factors that moderate consumption methods and probiotic survival.

A simulation of the GI tract with various issues, such as gastroparesis, a condition of gastric functions in which gastric emptying is delayed (Mandarino, 2023), or dumping syndrome, a condition of stomach contents being rapidly emptied into the small intestine (Cleveland Clinic, 2026), will elucidate the effects these conditions have on the probiotic survivability.

CONCLUSION

This study investigates the effects of beverages on the survivability of LGG in a simulated upper intestinal tract model. Among the three trials, there was an increased LGG survivability in the stomach stage when using acidic drinks (coffee and Monster Energy®), as compared to water, whereas the LGG survivability in the duodenum was comparable across all beverage treatments. This study found that the overall LGG survivability was higher as compared to the original Bayer et al. (2025) study. Capsules were found to be a more effective delivery method, regardless of the beverage, for retaining the bacteria and dispersing them at the appropriate time. This is possible because the capsule composition enables a time-release mechanism with a less confining matrix than chewable tablets. Future studies include improving the simulated upper intestinal tract model, investigating LGG survival in foods, and exploring probiotic survivability in altered models to reflect real-life medical variations.

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COVER

Katie Brunton

AACC Visual Arts Student

Black Cat, 2026

Acrylic on bristol

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